

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KAPADIA****FIRST NAME: DHRUTI****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Introduction (**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7**)
2. American vs British English (**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25**)
3. Meaning of plagiarism(**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34**)
4. When to give credit (**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34**)
5. Chicago Style and Usage(**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44**)
6. Capitalization (**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44**)
7. Footnotes(**Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 52**)

DIFFERENT STYLES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is a formal style of writing usually used in scholarly and educational contexts. This is for the purpose emphasising clarity and use of evidence which would help in supporting arguments. For any research paper, essays, and worldwide publications from the academic point of view.

Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal pros register, citations and references to other works, and use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

American vs British English - then in other aspects of the language pronunciation, grammar vocabulary spelling, punctuation, and formatting of dates and numbers. However, differences in written and most spoken grammar structures usually tend to be few works

then in other aspects of the language. There are many types of essays in this study material seen in the course.

American and British English are both variants of world English; we will stop as such; they are more similar than different, especially with “educated” or “scientific” English. Most divergence can be ascribed to different national histories and cultural development(cf. are Americans ruining English?[PBS] And the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25).

Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal pros register, citations and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research and advanced new contributions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

Meaning of Plagiarism- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Examples of plagiarism are taking someone else's word, such as quoting, Paraphrasing, copying and pasting from the Internet, and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

When to give credit to the author- when using any quote, paraphrase, statistics/data, or visuals(such as a graph) that are borrowed from another source (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

2) CHICAGO STYLE

a) Meaning

Chicago style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual of Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (Both published by the University of Chicago press). Well, sometimes references are made to a “Turabian Style,” This is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers, revised fall of 2006 (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44).

One of the best stylings from an academic's point of view is the Chicago style which is known as the Chicago Manual of Style in CMS, which deals with guidelines set out for writing and formatting documents that are usually seen in publications and worldwide known in circles of academics. the rules and this citation of how to prepare manuscript preparations and other aspects of writing are very professionally laid down in CMS.

b) Styles within Chicago Style

There are two divisions mainly seen within the Chicago style notes that is the bibliography style and the use of footnotes or north nodes, and the author-date style, which uses in-text citations and reference lists. It is important to note that this style, if well followed, will bring more effective writing in the academic circle.

Capitalization

Capitalisation follows important guidelines, which are as under:

Titles and headings- entitles and headings, which would include major nouns, pronounced verbs, adjectives, and adverbs along with any conjunction prepositions articles of 4 or more letters, for example, “birds are flying”.

Names and title - names that are names of people, places, and organisations.

Sentences and Paragraphs - use standard rules of capitalisation for sentences and paragraphs. the first word of the sentence is usually capitalised.

Text citation - according to the same rules, titles, and headings.

Bibliographies Entries - of each major word in the titles of books, commerce magazines, articles other works in the bibliography. however, prepositions, conjunctions, and articles with fewer letters are not usually until and unless it is the first word of the title.

Quotations- whenever one is quoting a source it is important to maintain original capitalisation unless it does not fit within the context of your sentence. you can use square brackets to make minor changes for clarity for grammatical correctness.

Section Headings- in Chicago style, these section headings often follow the basic capitalisation rules, which means which major words capitalised and shorter words like prepositions in lower case.

Dictionaries.“For general matters of spelling, Chicago recommends using Webster's 3rd new international dictionary and its chief abridgment, *Mariam- webster's collegiate dictionary*.... In its latest edition. If more than one spelling is given or more than one form of the plura..... Chicago normally opts for the first form listed, thus aiding consistency. If, as occasionally happens the collegiate disagrees with the 3rd international, the collegiate should be followed since it represents the latest lexical research” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44).

c) Foot Notes

Footnotes must be placed, or at least must begin, on the page add where they were referred to [indicated by a superscript numeral in the text.] a short rule or separator

separates the text and the footnotes. If a footnote runs over to the following page, a separator should be inserted on that page. Each footnote must begin on a new line, indented in the same amount as paragraphs in the footnotes, which are usually single-spaced with a blank line between notes (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 52).

It plays a very important role as it provides additional information or citation to a document without disrupting the main flow of the text Chicago-style footnotes are often used to provide explanations, references, or commentary on specific points in the text. there are certain methods by which the footnotes can be seen.

Inserting Footnotes - whenever you want to add a footnote, you can play a superscript number and insert it at the end of the sentence or phrase where you want to provide additional information.

Citations in footnotes- when citing sources, footnotes used in appropriate format would create ready information about where the context has been taken.

3) CONCLUSION

In the overview of the entire material in this course, it is clear that academic writing really needs a specialised training in order to do proper research so that this follows get their hands and knowledge on how to present the papers, books, and anything they do in the research field. I would emphasise Chicago style academic writing conclusion since I have taken my topic in this paper to give more detailing about what I have understood from it; in short, it would mean that how the significant findings were arguments restate the statement with different footnotes with appropriate publications credits and styling of the fonts which would enable viewers and videos to appreciate and from where the source of information is which is added in the publication.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Central African Republic.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.